

The Searching for Analyzing the USA Top States' GDP Variation Status by California~Illinois States & Pennsylvania~Georgia States & Maryland~Indiana Ones Accordingly through Sustainably Observing them

Run Xu^{1*}

^{1*}Gyeongsang National University, School of Nano New Materails Eng.,
Jinju-Si 52828, Gyeongsangnam-Do, South Korea.

***Correspondence:** Run Xu

Received: 01-February-2025
Accepted: 20-February-2026
Published: 23-February-2026

Copyright © 2026, Authors retain copyright. Licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.
<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/> (CC BY 4.0 deed)

This article is published in the **MSI Journal of Economics and Business Management (MSIJEBM)**

ISSN 3049-141X (Online).

The journal is managed and published by MSI Publishers.

Volume: 3, Issue: 2 (February-2026)

ABSTRACT: The GDP as an indicating economy would have a significant effect, so that the variation status might influence the whole national economic level & quality gradually because the China already entered into the 13 ten thousand dollars threshold that will be a developing milestone. We should continue to develop to 20 ten thousand dollars one sustainably through utilizing our nation people wisdom and behavior. It is believed that after ten year the new era can be open for us to experience and share. At the same time, the new quality productivity will become an indication direction that can be cultivated from now on so as to acquire a high-technology & high-sustainability one. Like Winder turbine, Photovoltaic voltage, nuclear-reaction piles, low-air economy etc that definitely can bring out new innovation behavior for instructing further advanced technology. Thereby, the high-tech production would occupy the most part for us to pursue the high-efficiency and high-level environment that might become our further destination for producing more innovation production continually. So that the enough educating new engineer and talents enable us to process more space for

searching more functional ones with more diversities business. Because those diversities may make our life to become more convenient and comfortable through endeavoring our engineers and experts for the sake of positively participating their each research theme and making an interesting conception under main principles. In USA the more sophisticated project will affect their GDP enhancement through widely collecting the world top scientists and scholars to process more deepening research and science that may occupy their first-one country with stabilized leading effectiveness. From California to Missouri state the higher GDP would reflect the entire nation quality and level through the aeronautics out-space exploration lunar landing etc. a series of scientific research are able to continually process that makes the USA to become No. 1 in mostly all of the fields. Even they proceeded the Mars etc. approaching and rotating & landing works many years ago. Moreover, they owned the most amount nuclear weapons with several thousands that may destroy the whole earth once the nuclear war happens. So we should pay more attention to the USA who may affect its role in every aspects in the earth. Thereby, China will raise up becoming the second GDP big country who may prohibit USA military and limit its development and enlarging behavior too.

Keywords: *Searching for, analyzing; California~Illinois, States; Pennsylvania~Georgia States, Maryland~Indiana, the USA GDP Variation, by sustainably observing*

1. Introduction

The GDP which indicates national economic status has provided an important role in every aspect in the world. So that the population increasing rate would be maintained for the sake of raising high-technique product with the entire industrial chain constantly which might enhance our new-quality-productivity. Hence we should consider the effective factors for example the population quantity, new quality productivity with high-technique etc. like big plane electric vehicle battery AI robot quantum computer medicine making disease diagnosis AI (artificial intelligence), ocean source space exploration nuclear generator etc. other ones. Low population is enable to offer high life & quality with improving GDP per capita value. Meanwhile, it can enhance the national whole GDP value and help us to boost the economic

recovery and many things to do. So the certain population is about to improve our national confidence some degree and make us to become priority one as early as possible even the super-country to lead the world to leadership right.

In contrast, the GDP increasing rate may play a significant role with regulating population increasing rate mutually and cooperatively. Hence the two aspects may be emphasized and paid attention to in thriving the whole national economic developed degree through enough wielding our generations positively and efficiently by our government institution endeavor and evaluation. For the sake of making relevant policies and allocating capital into the necessary industries the corresponding strategic plan needs to be made under various background and entities. Then the according monitor and estimation will be followed and estimated periodically and frequently by the observer in government's institution. At last as to the developed speed in one nation the corresponding population increasing quantity and high-technique product producing will be discussed and considered more preciously and correctly according to the near past years experience and variation.

Therefore, the high-technique products will be completed through wielding our scientist & senior Engineers coordination tightly for the sake of reviving the industrial and tertiary modernization. We should constantly look for and seek the new quality productivity sustainably so as to take place of our traditional industry becoming modernity. An innovation industry like new energy electric generator will be in front of our path forwards, so that the corresponding tactic must be put up and seek the opportunity and fortune in order to burden our responsibility quickly and not to forget recommend the fitting one to appoint new occupation. Like the Bole identified horse or Maosui self-recommended the recommendation will be represent one aspect for our human resource department to consider and evaluate the recommended included a full research room with a set of computer high-technique instrument & device, subordinate, subsidiary staff, salary, house, welfare etc. a series of work so as to appoint his new occupation reasonably and willingly. [1~17]

2. Discussions

For the sake of welcoming the demand we should educate a lot of scientist and experts candidates from university department to college & institution one to take the

high scholar degree for them to grasp one foreign language and skill to apply to futural requirement and practice. In university, the class with taking more practice education and experience and good teacher proceed the more competition teaching and theoretical and practical combination class to prepare for using after their graduate from college. Meantime, the enhancing GDP factors will include the high-technique products and its whole industrial chains and high-intelligence product that may influence the service business mostly. So we should increase those high-profit & high-tech skill for making more advance products so as to improve our service business level and quality & effectiveness at all. So that we should maintain and develop the tertiary industry continuously under controlling the second one. With the life quality enhancing continually the service one is about to wield its effectiveness presently and in futural long time, thereby we should follow up the changed situation and own independent capacity to master one outstanding skill to satisfy the futural request in advance. [18~22]

2.1 The USA GDP variation status

The USA GDP with top five sates' variation status analysis would show 1,533~544 billion yuan by California~Illinois states accordingly explained the California one strong economy strength and capacity in 2003 in light of Figure 1. The y-y value might indicate 6.2%~4.5% by them respectively recorded their modest growth step. In contrast, the Florida one maintained the fastest step with 8.3%. whilst the New York state finished the slowest 4.2%.

Figure 1. The USA GDP with top five sates' variation analysis. [1]

Furthermore, the USA GDP with top states' variation status analysis would show 470~351 billion yuan by Pennsylvania~Georgia states accordingly explained the Pennsylvania one strong economy strength and capacity in 2003 in light of Figure 2. The y-y value might indicate 5.1%~5.7% by them respectively recorded their modest growth step. In contrast, the Michigan state finished the slowest 3%.

Figure 2. The USA GDP six~ten states' status analysis. [1]

Furthermore, the USA GDP with top three states' variation status analysis would show 870~480 billion yuan by California~Texas states accordingly explained the California one strong economy strength and capacity in 1994 in light of Figure 3. The y-y value might indicate 4.7%~7.5% by them respectively recorded their modest growth step. In contrast, the New York state finished the slowest 4.6%.

Figure 3. The USA states' GDP variation analysis. [1]

Furthermore, the USA GDP with top states' variation status analysis would show 350~330 billion yuan by Illinois~Florida states accordingly explained their strong economy strength and capacity in 1994 in light of Figure 4. The y-y value might indicate 6.5%~8.5% by them respectively recorded their faster growth step.

Figure 4. The USA states' GDP variation analysis I. [1]

Furthermore, the USA GDP with top states' variation status analysis would show 123~130 billion yuan by Maryland~Indiana states accordingly explained their strong economy strength and capacity in 1992 in light of Figure 5. The y-y value might indicate 5%~6.5% by them respectively recorded their moderate growth step.

Figure 5. The USA states' GDP variation analysis II. [1]

At the end, the USA GDP with top states' variation status analysis would show about 116 billion yuan by Minnesota~Missouri states accordingly explained their strong economy strength and capacity in 1992 in light of Figure 6. The y-y value might indicate 6%~4.9% by them respectively recorded their modest growth step.

Figure 6. The USA states' GDP variation analysis III. [1]

3. Conclusions

The GDP as an indicating economy would have a significant effect, so that the variation status might influence the whole national economic level & quality gradually because the China already entered into the 13 ten thousand dollars threshold that will be a developing milestone. We should continue to develop to 20 ten thousand dollars one sustainably through utilizing our nation people wisdom and behavior. It is believed that after ten year the new era can be open for us to experience and share. At the same time, the new quality productivity will become an indication direction that can be cultivated from now on so as to acquire a high-technology & high-sustainability one. Like Winder turbine, Photovoltaic voltage, nuclear-reaction piles, low-air economy etc that definitely can bring out new innovation behavior for instructing further advanced technology. Thereby, the high-tech production would occupy the most part for us to pursue the high-efficiency and high-level environment that might become our further destination for producing more innovation production continually. So that the enough educating new engineer

and talents enable us to process more space for searching more functional ones with more diversities business. Because those diversities may make our life to become more convenient and comfortable through endeavoring our engineers and experts for the sake of positively participating their each research theme and making an interesting conception under main principles. In USA the more sophisticated project will affect their GDP enhancement through widely collecting the world top scientists and scholars to process more deepening research and science that may occupy their first-one country with stabilized leading effectiveness. From California to Missouri state the higher GDP would reflect the entire nation quality and level through the aeronautics out-space exploration lunar landing etc. a series of scientific research are able to continually process that makes the USA to become No. 1 in mostly all of the fields. Even they proceeded the Mars etc. approaching and rotating & landing works many years ago. Moreover, they owned the most amount nuclear weapons with several thousands that may destroy the whole earth once the nuclear war happens. So we should pay more attention to the USA who may affect its role in every aspects in the earth. Thereby, China will raise up becoming the second GDP big country who may prohibit USA military and limit its development and enlarging behavior too.

Funding

This work was supported by the Korean Science & Engineering Fund (KSEF) under the granted No. 96-0300-11-01-03 with the Specified Basis Research program.

References

1. The USA GDP variation status, Feb. 115, 2026
2. Run Xu, Zhiqing Chen, The Study on Simulation of Resistance in Stall Motor [J], Journal of Electronic & Information Systems, 2020, April 02 (1):18~20, DOI:<https://doi.org/10.30564/jeis,v2i1,2045> Google Scholar, CrossRef, Scilit,Cnki
3. Run Xu, An Innovation Searching for Prospering Economy GDP Enhancement with Osaka & Shanghai and Hong Kong Cities & Shandong and Fujian Provinces on Scientists' Analysizing Behavior and Judgement by Sustainability, UKR Journal of Economics, Business and Management, Volume 1, Issue 10, 2025, 303~307 Impact factor 4.33

4. Run Xu, An Innovation Searching for Prospering Financial Reformation e.g. ETF and Economy GDP Enhancement with Indian Cities & Shandong and Fujian Provinces on Scientists' Analyzing Behavior and Judgement by Sustainability, UKR Journal of Economics, Business and Management, Volume 1, Issue 10, 2025, 308~313
5. Run Xu, An Innovation Searching for Prospering Financial Reformation e.g. ETF and Economy GDP Enhancement with G20 Group etc. on Scientists' Behavior and Judgement with Sustainability, UKR Journal of Economics, Business and Management, Volume 1, Issue 10, 2025, 184~188 Impact factor 4.33
6. Run Xu, An Innovation Searching for Prospering Financial Reformation e.g. ETF and Economy GDP Enhancement with Hubei & Hunan Provinces on Scientists' Published Behavior and Judgement by Sustainability, UKR Journal of Economics, Business and Management, Volume 1, Issue 10, 2025, 204~208 Impact factor 4.33
7. Run Xu, The Relationship of Properties with Variable Mass of Block on Crank Linkage Mechanism in Multibody System, (American) SunText Review of Material Science, 2021, S1: 105 Crossref, Goolge scholar Impact factor 2.6
8. Run Xu, Boyong Hur, A Simulation between Torque and Angle with Speed on Five Freedoms of Robot Mechanical Arm in Multibody Systems, Saudi Journal of Civil Engineering, 2021, 5(5): 91~93 Impact factor 1.2
9. Run Xu, Boyong Hur, The Relationship between Force and Time with Lagrange Equation by Regulating Piston Mass on Crankshaft of Vehicle, Saudi Journal of Engineering and Technology, 2021,6(4): 73-76 Impact factor 1.2
10. Run Xu, Jiaguang Liu, The Kinematics Model Establishment of Crank and Linkage with Time under Low Speed in Vehicle, 2021,6(4):67~72,Saudi Journal of Engineering and Technology, 2021,6(4): 57~61, DOI: 10.36348/sjet,2021,v06i04,004 Impact factor 1.2
11. Run Xu, The Kinematic Models of Crank with Angle and Time in Motor Housing Process, (American) SunText Review of Material Science, 2021, S1: 104, DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.51737/2766-5100,2021,S1,004> Impact factor 2.6, Scilit, Crossref, Google Scholar

12. Run Xu, The Modelling between Force & Torque and Crank Angle on Crank Linkage of Engine in Vehicle by Lagrange Formula I, Scholars International Journal of Chemistry and Material Sciences, 2021, 4(4): 36-39,DOI: 10.36348/sijcms,2021,v04i04,005
13. Run Xu, The Dynamic Modelling of Vortex Axis Blade between Speed, Force and Rotation under Variable Angle & Power in Helicopter, (American) SunText Review of Material Science, 2021,S1: 103
14. Run Xu, The Study of Relationship between Current and Acceleration on Simulation in Motor, (American) SunText Review of Material Science, 2021, S1: 101, Impact factor 2.6, Scilit, Crossref
15. Run Xu, Sugun Lim, Discussions to African Development of Technology and Innovation in its Industry, Scholars International Journal of Chemistry and Material Sciences,2021,4 (11):314~317
16. Run Xu, Sugun Lim, Younwook Kim, African Mechanism Involving in Transgenic product & Hydrogen Fuel in its Industry, Cross Current International Journal of Economics, Management and Media Studies, 2022,4(1): 1~4
17. Run Xu^{1*}, Wanhao Wu, Guanghui Yu, An Innovation Searching for Boosting GDP Increasement with European Union & China GDP comparison on Scientist Publishing Papers at Journal Sustainably, EDU REKHA INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP, ECONOMICS AND BUSINESS MANAGEMENT, Volume-2, Issue-1(January - February) 2026, 25~29
18. Run Xu¹, Wanhao Wu, Guanghui Yu, An Innovation Searching for Boosting GDP Increasement with 2026 Companies Ranking in Top Hundred Innovation and President Graduated from Zhejiang University for Companies on Scientist Publishing Papers at Subject for the International Journal of Engineering and Science Invention etc. Sustainably, UAI J Econ Bus Manag,Volume-II Issue-I (January–February) 2026, 42~45

19. Run Xu, An Innovation Searching for Prospering Financial Reformation like Stock's Sectors Increasing Amount and Economy GDP & its Per Capita Enhancement on Scientists Sustainably, UKR Journal of Economics, Business and Management, Volume 1, Issue 10, 2025, 153~157 Impact factor 4.33
20. Run Xu, An Innovation Searching for Prospering Economy GDP Enhancement with Different Regions on Scientists with Sustainability, UKR Journal of Economics, Business and Management, Volume 1, Issue 10, 2025, 148~152 Impact factor 4.33
21. Run Xu, An Innovation Searching for Prospering Financial Reformation like ETF and Economy GDP Enhancement on Scientists by Sustainability, UKR Journal of Economics, Business and Management, Volume 1, Issue 10, 2025, 143~147
22. Run Xu, Changfu Jin, An Innovation Searching for Prospering Financial Reformation like ETF and Economy GDP with Different Regions Enhancement on Scientists by Sustainability, UKR Journal of Economics, Business and Management, Volume 1, Issue 10, 2025, 139~142
23. Run Xu, Convergence Proving of the Theoretical & True Elongation Inequalities by Derivation and Analogy[J], Journal of Metallic Material Research, 2020, April 3(1): 15~19, DOI:<https://doi.org/10.30564/jmmr.v3i1.1757> Scopus, Google Scholar, CrossRef, Cnki